

Triggering the Buy: A Study on Impulse Purchasing Behavior and Consumption Patterns in Mumbai

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Abstract

In a city like Mumbai - India's financial capital - pulsing with advertisements, both digital and in-store retail mega-giants, impulse buying has become more than just a mere habit. Today, with the various marketing strategies employed by retailers, and, together with growing economic stability and digital convenience-based payments, impulse buying has become a reflection of Mumbai's bustling retail culture. This study explores impulse buying and consumption patterns among Mumbai residents through a mixed methodology approach, combining primary research data obtained from a questionnaire with secondary sources such as academic literature. Together with the empirical data and secondary sources, the research paper reveals key triggers of impulse purchases, including both physical and emotional triggers. Key findings highlight that while younger consumers are more akin to impulse buying, middle-aged consumers are also driven towards impulse spending through factors like income level, credit loans, lifestyle, and access to digital platforms.

Keywords: impulse buying, consumerism, convenience, consumption, digital, in-store

1. Introduction

Impulse buying, also known as impulse purchases, is commonly defined as a spontaneous and unplanned decision to purchase. Impulse buying occurs when “a consumer experiences a sudden, often powerful and persistent urge to buy something immediately” [1]. Rook further elaborates that, unlike planned or thoughtful purchases that might fit into a consumer’s shopping routine, an impulse buy often interrupts this routine, occurring suddenly and unexpectedly. Impulse buying can also be an effect of various consumer traits, exacerbated by marketing strategies that engage consumers’ senses to influence their perceptions of the products marketed and their behaviors. Clear and noticeable special schemes, discounts, and offers play a role in tricking the consumer’s mind into making quick, unplanned purchases by creating a sense of urgency or perceived value [2].

In the context of India, economic and environmental changes such as the changes made in the 1980s aimed to alleviate India’s stagnant growth and high poverty levels. In the 1990s, economic growth picked up, production expanded, better-quality consumer goods became more accessible, and higher disposable incomes improved the standard of living for many people [3]. This growing wealth gap highlights how urban areas, with higher disposable incomes and greater exposure to advertising, malls, and digital marketplaces, play a much larger role in driving impulse buying compared to rural regions.

Mumbai, India’s financial capital, stands at the heart of this analysis. Mumbai (or Bombay, as it was referred to until 1995) emerged in the 17th century. The city began to emerge as a significant urban center in the seventeenth century, following its transfer from Portuguese to British control. During the colonial era, Mumbai was the ‘Gateway’ to India in colonial days, and it remains so even today as a commercial port city, leading to the British shifting their headquarters from Surat to Mumbai [4]. The study further states that by the mid-eighteenth century, Mumbai had overtaken Surat as the leading port on India’s western coast and established itself as a key hub for trade. Post the India–Pakistan partition, many gravitated to Mumbai, and hence the population skyrocketed. Today, Mumbai is home to over 20 million people, some originally from the city, and others migrants from all across the country, bringing

their diverse cultures and businesses along with them. Industrial giants like the Ambani and Tata families have played a crucial role in shaping Mumbai's global and economic identity. Mukesh Ambani's Reliance Industries and the Tata Group have headquarters in the city, influencing sectors such as telecommunications, energy, retail, and steel, inviting in turn employment opportunities and a higher standard of living.

Thus, the significance of Mumbai lies not just in its economic stature as headquarters to major financial institutions and many multinational corporations, but also in its role as a trendsetter for consumer habits across the country. This article focuses on surveying impulse consumer behavior in the city and examining the factors that shape consumerist behavior in urban Mumbai.

2. Literature Survey

Several studies have examined the factors influencing impulse buying behavior in the Indian context. Sudan S. and co-worker use Hofstede's cultural framework to show that cultural dimensions such as collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation are negatively associated with impulse buying tendencies among Indian consumers [5]. This highlights the role of cultural values in shaping purchasing behavior. In their study on consumer trait perspective in the Indian context, Atulkar S. and co-workers emphasize psychological traits, finding that impulse buying is closely linked to low self-control and emotional reactivity, particularly among urban consumers in Central India [6]. Together, these studies suggest that both internal traits and external stimuli, shaped by cultural and contextual factors, significantly affect impulse buying in India.

Huo C. and team use the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) framework to investigate how live-streaming commerce affects impulsive purchasing behavior [7]. Sales promotions and social presence (engagement and interaction during live streams) are identified as important stimuli that improve the consumer's flow experience, which in turn encourages impulsive purchases. Additionally, the study

discovered that time and financial resources amplify this effect. The study, which was based on a survey of 375 Chinese consumers, offers both theoretical insights into the literature on live-streaming and impulse buying as well as useful advice for marketers looking to improve their strategies by utilizing situational factors, engagement, and promotions.

The goal of an exploration on e-impulse buying by Singh S. and co-workers was to identify and examine the main factors that influence e-impulse buying in the Indian context [8]. It divides the main stimuli into extrinsic (like discounts, product quality, website design, and brand trust) and intrinsic (like a customer's innate propensity to make impulsive purchases) factors. The study emphasizes that although Indian consumers are extremely price sensitive, they also value product quality and appearance. Additionally, a website's quality and clarity, as well as its promotional messaging and efficient communication, all have a big impact on encouraging impulsive purchases. By thoroughly examining these elements, the study not only closes a gap in the body of knowledge but also offers insightful information to online merchants hoping to improve customer service. In terms of food consumption, an examination of India's shifting rural-urban consumption trends by Gupta S. and team uses data from the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), showing that the percentage of spending on food items decreased significantly over the years, while non-food expenditures rose. Both rural and urban areas reflect this trend, with rural areas historically devoting a larger portion to food but progressively catching up to urban spending patterns. The results point to a shift in consumer behavior toward diversified consumption, which reflects India's shifting lifestyles and overall economic development [9].

The literature survey revealed that there have not been many studies on impulse buying and consumption patterns previously done in Mumbai; hence, this study, conducted using primary and secondary research, poses a relevant addition to understanding urban Mumbai's existing and developing impulse buying habits and can offer a pathway towards understanding future consumption patterns.

3. Methodology

A Microsoft Forms questionnaire was created. The questionnaire contains questions under three main sections: Demographic Information, Analysis of Social Media Influence, and Analysis of Shopping Behavior. The questionnaire was then distributed among mixed crowds with no preference towards any age, class, or gender. Some of the media of distribution included those among social circles, friend groups, and family. Responses were submitted over a span of two weeks. The results were then analyzed through observations and graphical analysis, and interpretation. Microsoft Excel was used to generate graphs and draw trendlines from the data collected. The link to the questionnaire is available through the following link.

<https://forms.cloud.microsoft/r/kx1z5ucMcE>

4. Findings

The demographic data from the survey showcases Mumbai city's social diversity, with a male-to-female ratio of 39:50, including one respondent identifying as diverse. This reflects Mumbai's inclusive nature. The questionnaire reached a broad respondent age range, though the majority of respondents were 41-60 years old, possibly because of the large middle-aged working population in the city. In terms of education, most respondents held postgraduate degrees, indicating a well-educated group, but also highlighting the limitation of a substantial amount of input from individuals from a less educated background. In terms of salary, 65% were salaried and 22% were unemployed, indicating an intricate blend of financial stability and financial dependence - including individuals such as housewives, students, or retirees who might rely on allowances or alternative forms of support. The income distribution among middle-income brackets was mostly even, with 28 respondents in each ₹5-10 lakh and ₹11-20 lakh annual income ranges, and 39 in the ₹21-50 lakh bracket. This highlights a strong economic middle-class presence, also shedding light on possible spending habits, but limiting input for individuals earning below the minimum income bracket provided. The most popular social media platforms are WhatsApp, YouTube, and Instagram, showing how closely daily life and social media have become. Additionally, the platforms also highlight the growing Western influence on the Indian masses. With the exposure to many different digital social media platforms,

respondents' screen time varied from 0.5 to 6.6 hours. Most buying decisions were largely affected by exposure to a large variety of products, presumably both online and in-store, with new and hyped up trends that drive consumerism. Along with buying decisions, the categories respondents spent the most on included clothing and accessories and food and beverages. 52% favored shopping online and 46% in-store reflecting close but growing inclination towards online shopping.

5. Discussion

Figure 1. The analysis of the preferred social media application of the respondents. WhatsApp, YouTube, and Instagram turned out to be popular platforms.

The data (**Figure 1**) highlights the most preferred social media platforms among users, with WhatsApp, YouTube, and Instagram leading significantly. In the context of Mumbai's urban landscape, these platforms play a major role in driving impulse buying. WhatsApp enables product sharing and small business promotions, group chat buying and selling, thus fostering quick and trust-based impulse buying. YouTube and Instagram, on the other hand, aim to influence a larger audience with their catchy product advertisements and influencer promotions. Instagram also acts as a major hub for both homegrown and international businesses to promote their product firsthand and build a loyal consumer base through short reels and routine posts.

Overall, the fast-growing social media applications are reminiscent of Mumbai's constant and instantaneous buying habits.

Figure 2. The analysis of the buying stages of respondents most affected by social media. Exposure to a variety of products and services surpasses the others.

The data (**Figure 2**) reveals that in Mumbai, social media has the greatest influence during the exposure stage of the buying decision. This is evident as over 50% of respondents indicate that exposure to a variety of products has influenced their buying decisions. Additionally, the growing market in Mumbai has given rise to newer e-commerce shopping applications in recent years, allowing consumers to search for alternatives and similar products differing in price or quality. This highlights the cautiousness and the inherent need to find better quality and cheaper prices.

Figure 3. The analysis of the shopping categories that respondents spend the most on. Clothing, fashion, food, and beverages take the highest spending

The data (**Figure 3**) indicates that in Mumbai, the highest spending is on Clothing and Fashion Accessories, followed by Food and Beverages, and Travel and Experiences. This reflects the city's fast-paced and socially active lifestyle. In a metropolitan hub like Mumbai, fashion trends spread rapidly via social media and peer influence, and thus spending on clothing and fashion, and dining out is common. This phenomenon is especially evident among youth and working professionals influenced by peers and coworkers. The socially active lifestyle in the city also creates the urge to fit in and be one with the masses, following new and upcoming fashion and elitist trends at the cost of credit loans for many.

High engagement in gadgets and electronics, and entertainment also highlights the city's tech-savvy culture. In contrast, toys and games, and kitchen items receive the least spending, suggesting that family-oriented purchases are less frequent among the primary urban consumer base surveyed, and there is a growing shift towards digital games, especially in the current generation. This overall pattern shows that social, influenced by the citizens' urge to earn more and thus spend more, and lifestyle-driven consumption dominates spending behavior in Mumbai

Figure 4. The analysis of the preferred mode of shopping by consumers. Online beats in-store shopping by a small margin.

Figure 5. The analysis of respondents' go to quick commerce app. Swiggy Instamart, Blinkit, and Zepto remain the most popular.

(Figure 4) shows that online shopping is the most preferred mode of shopping among consumers in Mumbai, slightly overtaking in-store shopping. This reflects the city's growing dependence on convenience-based and quick digital shopping platforms with streamlined payment options.

However, the high number of in-store shoppers also highlights Mumbai’s retail culture, where many still enjoy physically experiencing products, especially for fashion and food, with their loved ones. Thrifting and other modes still remain niche, possibly due to limited awareness and social stigma around thrifting and buying second-hand clothes, even associating it with a low socioeconomic status. Overall, the trend suggests that while digital consumption is on the rise, traditional retail still holds strong in Mumbai’s retail ecosystem. Following the rise of online shopping, according to the other set of data [Figure 5], Swiggy Instamart is the most frequently used quick commerce app among Mumbai consumers, followed by Zepto and Blinkit. This suggests a strong preference for platforms that offer fast delivery of groceries and other essentials even at discounted prices, aligning with the city’s need for convenience and saving time.

Figure 6. The analysis of the shopping categories purchased exclusively online by respondents. Food and movie tickets remain on top.

Interestingly, apps like BookMyShow and MakeMyTrip also received responses, indicating that while not traditionally considered “quick commerce,” they are essential platforms for entertainment and travel, which are integral to urban consumption in Mumbai. TATA 1mg and Nature’s Basket have a smaller presence, possibly catering to

specific needs like pharmaceuticals and personal health and hygiene shopping. The data (**Figure 6**) shows that food and movie tickets are the most common categories that consumers in Mumbai now purchase exclusively online. This reflects the city's strong digital infrastructure and the popularity of digital platforms like Swiggy, Zomato, and BookMyShow that help alleviate inconvenience and the overall consumer experience, making it as seamless as possible. Travel bookings and clothing/accessories also see high online consumption, indicating a shift in consumer trust toward e-commerce for holiday planning and entertainment needs. Interestingly, BookMyShow is favored for booking movie tickets mostly, despite the convenience and service fees consumers have to pay on top of ticket prices, instead of just going to the cinema and avoiding extra charges. Whilst a niche observation, one can infer that Mumbai's growing financial stability is because a large portion of people are earning more. The lower numbers for medicine and gadgets suggest that while these categories are growing online, many consumers still prefer in-store purchases for assurance, physical verification, or immediate needs. Overall, the trend highlights how Mumbai's urban consumers are increasingly turning to digital platforms for regular and recreational purchases.

The data (**Figure 7**) reveals that UPI is the most preferred payment method among consumers in Mumbai, followed by credit cards. This reflects the city's adaptation towards cashless modes of payment, such as through UPI platforms like GooglePay, Paytm, and PhonePe, which allow for a seamless and cashless money transfer experience. These platforms have a growing popularity because now, one need not worry about carrying all their bank account cards with them; instead, these all-in-one UPI platforms allow for digital integration with your mobile phone and help keep all payment history in one place. However, credit cards are also widely used, suggesting that a substantial sample still values the benefits of reward programs and credit-building opportunities that credit cards offer, highlighting a continued reliance on traditional financial tools, which also took years to reach a large audience and gain their trust since their launch in India in the 1980s. Cash still maintains a notable presence, indicating that while digital payments dominate, physical transactions remain relevant, like when shopping in local markets or making small purchases that can be made without credit loans or having to use a debit card. Additionally, cash may

also be preferred by certain merchants in local markets who are not familiar with digital payments or do not trust them, yet, indicating that there is still room for growing awareness about digital cashless payment for the lower-income earning bracket.

Figure 7. The analysis of the preferred payment methods for purchases. UPI and Credit cards are most widely used.

The data (**Figure 8**) reveals that the availability of discounts/sales plays the biggest trigger among consumers in Mumbai, followed by return policies. This reflects the highly value-driven and product quality mindset that prevails in the city, where shoppers, mostly of the middle-income earning bracket, are motivated by savings and promotional offers. Consumers might also be influenced by the ability to easily return purchases they find unsuitable at little to no courier or convenience fees from the comfort of their homes. Return policies are largely popular on digital shopping platforms as consumers have the incentive to return items knowing that there is a payback guarantee, as opposed to shopping in-store and having to inconveniently travel to return items. Google reviews, whilst not preferred by many, is still an upcoming way for consumers to get first-hand product reviews and thus make calculated choices before purchasing.

Figure 8. The analysis of the biggest trigger factors for making purchases, discounts/sales, and return policies remains prominent.

Figure 9. The analysis of the biggest purchase influences. The majority of respondents state that their purchases are not influenced by anybody.

The data (**Figure 9**) indicates that almost half, 49% of respondents, believe their shopping behavior is not influenced by anyone. This highlights the possibility of several secondary factors, such as financial independence and emotional maturity, that influence individual shopping behaviors. At 17% and 11% respectively, friends and romantic relationships are especially important in categories like fashion, food, and lifestyle, where shared preference and validation of choices often matter. Meanwhile, elders and siblings exert less influence, suggesting that shopping decisions, particularly among younger, urban individuals, are becoming increasingly self-dependent and digitally informed through reviews and self-research before making purchases, with social circles having more influence. This reflects a shift in Mumbai's urban consumer landscape toward individualized, independent purchasing behavior.

Figure 10. The analysis of the frequency of purchases made.

The data (**Figure 10**) shows that shopping frequency among Mumbai consumers is mostly evenly spread out, with the highest number of respondents making purchases once a week, possibly for everyday essentials like groceries or personal products,

followed by those shopping once a month and once a fortnight. This indicates a blend of routine-based and need-based consumption, reflecting the fast-paced urban lifestyle of Mumbai, where regular purchases, especially for food, fashion, and daily essentials, are common and influenced by factors like convenience with applications and products available at one's fingertips. Interestingly, respondents shop more than twice a week, pointing to a segment of consumers highly engaged in impulse buying. Only 24 respondents shop once every three months, suggesting that infrequent, bulk-buying behavior is less common but highly suggested to avoid the occurrence of frequent impulse purchases.

Figure 11. The analysis of respondents' biggest concerns when making online purchases. Quality of items purchased remains the biggest concern.

The data (**Figure 11**) indicates that an astonishingly high number of respondents show concern about the quality of items purchased online, creating an interesting contrast between the city's fast-paced lifestyle and the detailed attention given to quality and a certain sense of unreliability on online shopping. While digital shopping is widespread, the emphasis on quality highlights a lingering trust barrier when

purchasing good online, especially those that are non-returnable or have a limited shelf life.

Figure 12. The analysis of respondents' feelings after making an impulse purchases.

The data (**Figure 12**) reveals that the majority of respondents feel neutral after making an impulse purchase, suggesting a normalized and detached relationship with unplanned buying, perhaps as a result of an individual becoming accustomed to frequent impulse purchases. Neutral emotions could also reflect the city's constant exposure to sales, ads, and influencer marketing, making impulse purchases feel more routine rather than surprising.

However, respondents reported feeling happy or satisfied, indicating that for many, impulse buying brings a sense of immediate gratification, often linked to lifestyle or mood enhancement. On the other hand, a smaller segment experiences anxiety or guilt/regret, highlighting the internal conflict some consumers face between spontaneous desires and battling with financial straits. Overall, while impulse buying is common, Mumbai's consumers exhibit a mix of emotional detachment, short-term joy, neutral emotions.

Figure 13. The analysis of respondents' willingness to spend money in a single offline purchase.

Figure 14. The analysis of the average money spent every month on impulse purchases.

(Figure 13) indicates that 35% of consumers would spend 3001 rupees and above in a single offline purchase, indicating that a significant number of people are comfortable spending higher amounts of money in stores. Spending more money in stores compared to online is still a habit for money because one knows of the quality, and durability of the item they get after touching and feeling it. Additionally, the assurance of actually getting the same product as chosen also draws people to spending more during offline shopping trips. On the contrary, 26% spend less than 1000 rupees during offline purchases suggesting small, frequent purchases. Spending less offline might also suggest more spending online for certain categories like clothing and accessories during discounts or offers while daily requirements are bought offline.

Over 55% of respondents indicate that their average monthly spending on impulse purchases is less than 1000 rupees, suggesting that for most, impulse buying may be budget-friendly and controlled. 36% spend between a moderate 1001-5000 rupees on impulse purchases every month indicating a niche respondent sample willing to spend more money on impule purchases (Figure 14).

Figure 15. The analysis of whether respondents check product reviews before making an impulse purchase.

A significant 58.5% of respondents always check product reviews before making an impulse purchase, indicating a high level of consumer caution and somewhat awareness even during spontaneous buying. Around 33.9% sometimes check, showing partial reliance on peer reviews and feedback. Only a small portion, 3.8%, rarely or never check reviews, suggesting that for most, complete trust in product quality and feasibility through reviews may not play an integral role in their buying decisions (**Figure 15**).

6. Conclusions and Perspectives

The research reveals the complex nature of Mumbai's urban consumerist landscape, shaped by a dynamic interplay of social, emotional, and economic triggers. The findings note that with the rise of digital payment platforms like UPI and netbanking, and exposure to advertisements and social circles, consumption patterns have been highly affected. People are now able to make payments more quickly and easily, with the digital payment process becoming more streamlined and offering loans and offers. The data also reveals that online shopping has become the most preferred mode of shopping due to growing accessibility and exposure to social media influences like livestreams, regular deals, and quick cashbacks that increase the sense of urgency and perceived value of products. This, along with an individual's emotional state, like happiness when receiving a paycheck or sadness due to a particular reason, in turn leads to impulse purchases made in the moment without much thought about repercussions. The instantaneous boost of dopamine when making a purchase, especially online from the comfort of one's home, further reinforces this behavior, creating a cycle of gratification that can be difficult to break. Over time, this has led to a normalization of impulsive spending habits, particularly among younger demographics who are more digitally active. Individuals in their youth are more susceptible to being influenced by peers and desires rather than rational budgeting or cautious decision making, especially when making big purchases using modes like credit card loans, which can drive an unemployed teen or youth into an unending debt cycle if they can't repay.

This research concludes that while digital platforms have shaped convenience and accessibility to a wide array of products and mastered the art of blurring the line between a need and a want, they have also intensified emotional and social triggers, as discussed earlier, that drive impulse buying. This underscores the pressing need for financial literacy and responsible money spending habits education for many, especially the urban youth capable of driving not only themselves but also others around them, like their social circle, into heavy debt as well. Comprehensive financial literacy programs included in secondary school and college programs can immensely benefit students and young adults about credit card debt and managing finances responsibly.

Additionally, adults can also be educated about the responsibilities of money expenditure with credit cards. It is also recommended that people channelize their wants and desires and make educated choices based on their income and savings. Oftentimes, earning a paycheck at the end of the month can lure many young professionals and working individuals into spending most of their income without dedicating some towards building healthy savings. On the part of online retailers, they also hold immense responsibility when it comes to ensuring ethical marketing practices, especially online through influencers being paid to promote products, and promoting informed purchasing decisions. This should be done so to ensure that consumers' psychological triggers are not exploited for mere profit, instead being engaged within healthy limits.

References

- [1] D. W. Rook, "The Buying Impulse," *Journal of Consumer Research*, vol. 14, no. 2, p. 189, Sep. 1987, doi: 10.1086/209105.
- [2] S. Atulkar and B. Kesari, "Impulse Buying: A Consumer Trait Prospective in Context of Central India," *Global Business Review*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 477–493, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1177/0972150917713546.
- [3] L. Ciochetto, "Advertising and Globalization in India," *Media Asia*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 157–169, Jan. 2004, doi: 10.1080/01296612.2004.11726750.
- [4] R. P. Misra, Ed., *Urbanisation in South Asia*. Foundation Books, 2012. doi: 10.1017/9789382993087.
- [5] S. W. Ali and S. Sudan, "Influence of Cultural Factors on Impulse Buying Tendency: A Study of Indian Consumers," *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 68–77, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1177/0972262917750247.
- [6] S. Atulkar and B. Kesari, "Impulse Buying: A Consumer Trait Prospective in Context of Central India," *Global Business Review*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 477–493, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1177/0972150917713546.
- [7] C. Huo, X. Wang, M. W. Sadiq, and M. Pang, "Exploring Factors Affecting Consumer's Impulse Buying Behavior in Live-Streaming Shopping: An Interactive Research Based Upon SOR Model," *Sage Open*, vol. 13, no. 2, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1177/21582440231172678.
- [8] S. Singh and H. Verma, "An exploration of e-impulse buying," *International Journal of Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 45, 2019, doi: 10.1504/IJEMR.2019.10017362.
- [9] S. Gupta and Prof. K. Singh, "An Analysis of Changing Rural-Urban Consumption Pattern in India," *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 21, no. 09, pp. 56–71, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.9790/0837-2109085671.

QUESTIONNAIRE

1.Email ID

2.Gender

- a. Male
- b. Female
- c. Diverse

3.Age

- a. 13-19
- b. 20-30
- c. 31-40
- d. 41-60
- e. 61 and above

4.Education

- a. 10+2 and below
- b. Graduation
- c. Post Graduation and above

5.Occupation

- a. Self Employed
- b. Daily wage
- c. Salaried
- d. Entrepreneur
- e. Unemployed

6.Annual Income (LPA)

- a. 0-4
- b. 5-10
- c. 11-20
- d. 21-50
- e. 51+

7.Preferred social media platforms

- a. Instagram
- b. TikTok
- c. YouTube
- d. Facebook
- e. Twitter
- f. WhatsApp
- g. Snapchat
- h. Reddit
- i. Pinterest
- j. Television (dish TV)

8.Average screen time dedicated to social media per week (in hours)

- a. 0.5-2

- b. 2.5-4
- c. 4.5-6
- d. 6.5+

9. In your opinion which stage of your buying decision has been mostly affected by social media?

- a. Exposure to variety of products and services
- b. Problem recognition/presenting the need for a purchase
- c. Search for alternatives and similar products
- d. Comparison of product price
- e. Evaluation of product information
- f. Post purchase evaluation

10. Which of the following categories do you spend on the most?

- a. Gadgets and Electronics
- b. Clothing and Fashion accessories
- c. Beauty and Skincare
- d. Home Decor and Furnishing
- e. Sports and Fitness Gear
- f. Books and Furnishing
- g. Food and Beverages
- h. Kitchen Utensils/Appliances and Crockery
- i. Travel and Experiences
- j. Entertainment
- k. Toys and Games

11. What is your preferred mode of shopping?

- a. In store
- b. Online
- c. Thrifting

12. Preferred online shopping platform

- a. Amazon
- b. Flipkart
- c. Myntra
- d. Meesho
- e. Urbanic
- f. WhatsApp shopping
- g. TikTok shopping
- h. Instagram shopping
- i. Facebook shopping
- j. Other Individual Brand websites

13. Go to quick commerce app?

- a. Blinkit
- b. Swiggy Instamart
- c. Zepto
- d. Big Basket
- e. Amazon Fresh

- f. TATA 1mg
- g. BookMyShow
- h. Make My Trip
- i. Nature's Basket

14. Which categories of purchases have you started making exclusively online?

- a. Travel
- b. Medicine
- c. Clothing and Accessories
- d. Food
- e. Movie Tickets
- f. Gadgets

15. What type of payment method do you prefer for purchases?

- a. Cash
- b. Credit card
- c. Debit card
- d. UPI
- e. Net Banking
- f. EMI
- g. I don't make online payments

16. What is the biggest trigger factor for making purchases?

- a. Cash on delivery
- b. Return policy
- c. Extended warranty
- d. Credit card EMI options
- e. Discounts/Sales
- f. Reusability of item
- g. Durability of item
- h. Social media
- i. Google reviews
- j. TV ads and variety
- k. Limited time offers
- l. Peer/family influence
- m. Emotional state (stress, happiness, boredom)

17. Who influences your purchases?

- a. Elders you know
- b. Kids you know
- c. Siblings
- d. Friends
- e. Relationship (partners)
- f. Not influenced by anybody

18. How often do you make purchases?

- a. Once a week
- b. More than twice a week
- c. Once a fortnight

- d. Once a month
- e. Months in three months

19. What are your biggest concerns when making purchases online?

- a. Safety
- b. Privacy
- c. Return policy
- d. Timely delivery
- e. Delivery of correct items
- f. Quality of items purchased

20. What is the ticket value that you would purchase in a single online purchase? (INR)

- a. Less than 1000
- b. 1000 to 5000
- c. 5000 to 10000
- d. 10000 and above

21. What is the ticket value that you would purchase in a single offline purchase? (INR)

- a. Less than 1000
- b. 1000 to 1500
- c. 1500 to 3000
- d. 3001 and above

22. Do you regret impulse purchases after buying?

- a. Always
- b. Sometimes
- c. Rarely
- d. Never

23. On average, how much do you spend on impulse purchases every month?

- a. Less than 1000
- b. 1001-5000
- c. 5001-10000
- d. 10000 and above

24. Do you check product reviews before making an impulse purchase?

- a. Always
- b. Sometimes
- c. Rarely
- d. Never

25. How do you feel after making an impulse purchase?

- a. Happy/Satisfied
- b. Guilty/Regretful
- c. Neutral
- d. Anxious about spending